

TEACHING CREATIVITY IN MECHANICAL DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a new method to teach creativity in mechanical design. The method is called ACRREx, which stands for Abstracting, Categorizing, Reflecting, Reformulating and Extending. By rejecting intuition-only designs and by offering more than just facilitating or stimulating idea generation, ACRREx is a systematic design method that uses categorization of knowledge to guide a designer to find “voids” in the knowledge, giving a good chance that innovative solutions can be found in those areas. ACRREx can be combined with other systematic design methods such as the Pahl & Beitz method as well as with intuitive design methods such as brainstorming and bio-inspired design. We teach ACRREx in our MSc course Bio-Inspired Design and to our graduation students. The results are fruitful and show the method’s potential for teaching creativity.

Keywords: bio-inspired, design, creativity.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching how to design creatively is difficult. While there are numerous methods to stimulate designers and to facilitate creative design processes, there are not many established methods that explicitly teach how to generate innovative design solutions. This paper describes a novel creative design method called ACRREx that we employ in our MSc course “Bio-Inspired Design” at TU Delft. This course teaches students how to use nature as a source of inspiration for designing clever technical devices. Whereas bio-inspiration alone does not guarantee innovative solutions, ACRREx is a systematic method to explore and expand the solution space in the search for new solution classes or entirely new

solution fields towards truly innovative answers to a design challenge.

In many fields of science and design, studying nature provides great inspiration, giving rise to new research fields such as bionics and biomimetics. At our Department Bio-Mechanical Engineering of TU Delft, bio-inspired research is being carried out on the design of novel surgical instruments inspired by working principles of biological creatures. Figure 1 shows an example of a steerable surgical forceps for laparoscopic surgery (surgery in the abdomen). The steerable tip contains a “Cable-Ring Mechanism” which was invented by investigating working principles of squid tentacles (Van Leeuwen & Kier, 1997) and mimicking tentacle anatomy with technical components (Breedveld & Scheltes, 2005; Breedveld et al., 2005; Breedveld 2010). As the mechanism contains only standard components or simple tubular shapes, it can be manufactured at lower costs and much smaller dimensions than conventional steerable instruments. The mechanism is patented worldwide and being commercialized by the medical industry for a range of surgical applications.

To train our students in transferring clever biological solutions to the technical domain, our MSc course Bio-Inspired Design, founded in 2006, aims at giving an overview of mechanical phenomena in nature and resulting bio-inspired designs. The course primarily targets mechanical and biomedical engineering students as well as students from other faculties such as industrial design. We teach them the working principles of a large variety of biological systems such as muscular hydrostatic skeleton systems, dry

Figure 1. Left: Soft-bodied octopus and cross section of Loliginid squid tentacle consisting of a muscular hydrostatic skeleton system of interacting muscles and employing a ring of muscle bundles for steering. Middle: patented Cable-Ring Mechanism employing a ring of cables for steering. Right: Cable-Ring Mechanism applied in steerable surgical grasper for laparoscopic surgery (shaft diameter 5 mm) that is about to enter the market (Breedveld, 2010).

and wet adhesive clamping methods, and spring balanced biological systems.

The course uses a project-based learning format with multidisciplinary teams of students from different faculties and departments. Each team is given a different design assignment that has to be solved in a structured and novel way, inspired by clever solutions from nature. Recent design assignments include single piece desk lamp, pick-up device for wheelchairs, span without scaffolds or cranes, easy method to carry babies in towns, deployable instrument, better door, robot cleaner, pram that can handle stairs, portable cooler, snow remover, mars rover for rough terrain, space manipulator, low friction steering mechanism, low energy transportation, non-slipping shoes, and trash bin that never gets dirty.

The course includes an introductory lecture, a series of lectures to show students working principles of biological systems and related bio-inspired designs, and four intermediate presentations of the student teams. We guide the teams to work on their assignment in the following sequence: problem analysis to identify the essence of the assignment, search for biological examples that may exhibit useful behaviors, bio-inspired concept designs, and final design. We encourage the teams to develop

prototypes to demonstrate their final design (by using e.g. LEGO, cardboard or computer simulations).

Bio-inspired design itself is a method to facilitate idea generation during the conceptual design phase (Chiu & Shu, 2007; Helms, Vattam & Goel, 2009; Shu et al. 2011), but it is not a systematic design method. During the introductory lecture at the beginning of the course we teach students to use a novel creative design method that we call the ACRREx method. ACRREx stands for Abstracting, Categorizing, Reflecting, Reformulating and Extending. Rather than just to facilitate or stimulate idea generation, for example by looking at designs in nature, ACRREx is a systematic design method that uses categorization of knowledge to guide a designer to find “voids” in the knowledge, with “void” meaning that no known design exists, giving a good chance that innovative solutions can be found in that direction. The ACRREx method can be used in combination with systematic design methods or inspiration methods. It helps designers to rationally elaborate design solutions obtained with those methods and improve them towards truly creative and innovative design solutions.

This paper describes the idea behind ACRREx and compares the method with the existing methods to

stimulate creative design processes. The ACRREx method is illustrated by a number of examples from design work carried out by our students.

BACKGROUND ON CREATIVE DESIGNING

According to Puccio, et al. (2010), for close to 60 years since Osborn's Creative Problem Solving (CPS) that came with brainstorming (Osborn, 1953), creativity has been a popular research topic in design, problem solving, and engineering education. In their opinion, representative work includes CPS (Osborn, 1953), lateral thinking of De Bono (1977), TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem Solving) of Altshuller (1984), and various types of "design thinking". Gero (2010) summarized research trends in design creativity and forecasts future research directions in the following areas:

- design processes including human creative design processes and biomimetic design,
- cognitive behavior,
- social interaction,
- cognitive neuroscience,
- measuring design creativity, and
- test suites of design tasks.

Among these (in particular in design process research), two contrasting methods are noted: one more systematic and procedural, and the other more intuitive. This was also observed by Shah in the context of machine design (1998). Some established examples of intuitive methods are brainstorming (Osborn, 1953), Method 635 (Rohrbach, 1969), Gallery method (Hellfritz, 1978), and Synectics (Gordon, 1961). Systematic approaches include so-called systematic design methodologies, such as Pahl & Beitz (2007) and Hubka (1982). It is somehow widely recognized that intuitive methods are more creative and capable of generating more innovative design solutions than systematic methods, while theoretically there is nothing in these systematic methods that prevents designers from becoming creative. Some exceptions of "systematic" methods as a means to become creative are proposed by Shah, et al. (2001) and Jin and Benami (2010).

While there is no established pedagogical method to teach creativity, particularly in engineering design,

teaching creativity has been emphasized and practiced by many educators. For instance, Camarda, et al. (2010) reported applications of a variety of teaching methods for innovative complex multi-disciplinary designs. Barak (2008) developed an engineering design course emphasizing innovative problems solving based on, among others, SCAMPER¹ (Eberle 1977), TRIZ (Altshuller, 1984), and SIT (Systematic Inventive Thinking)² developed by Horowitz and Maimon (1997). He points out that inventive problem solving should be guided by "idea focusing" rather than "idea generation".

From the viewpoint of idea generation in teaching creative design, we can identify two contrasting approaches. One covers indirect methods in which how to generate ideas is not clearly specified but idea generation is fostered, facilitated, or stimulated. For instance, brainstorming and Synectics are methods to foster creative thinking, but these methods themselves do not tell how to generate ideas. In this context, bio-inspired design is a stimulation method and does not tell how to generate ideas.

Other types of indirect idea generation facilitation include removing barriers that hinder achieving design solutions (typically TRIZ), and helping to get out of idea fixation (Jansson & Smith, 1991). In TRIZ (Altshuller, 1984), first a new design should be generated. When this design does not work, TRIZ helps to identify and break through obstacles that prevent the design from achieving the goal. Based on a large number of Soviet patents, Altshuller extracted a series of rules that can help this process.

In contrast, so-called systematic design methods are direct methods to procedurally generate new ideas. For example, the Pahl & Beitz method (2007) first decomposes functional requirements and establishes

¹ SCAMPER is a method to arrive at a new design by "Substitute" a component, "Combine" components, "Adapt" a function, "Modify" scale, etc., "Put" components into other uses, "Eliminate" elements, and "Reverse" operations.

² SIT consists of "Unification", "Multiplication", "Division", "Elimination", and "Change" operations.

function structure. Working principles that will realize sub functions will be searched for and combined to form a mechanism. Combinations of different principles are systematically generated resulting in a vast number of combinations from which the best solution will be selected based on certain criteria. Since combinations are systematically generated in this method, idea generation can be exhaustive and may include “creative designs”, although they are often merely new combinatorial varieties. Nagel, et al. (2010) proposed a bio-inspired concept generation method based on a transformational definition of functions, which can guide idea generation. Unfortunately, this method lacks generality, because it uses so-called transformational function definition (i.e., a function transforms energy, material, and signals) and forces to model even biological systems in this scheme.

In a previous paper (Tomiyama, et al., 2010) we reported an early version of ACRREx with a theoretical foundation based on General Design Theory (Yoshikawa, 1981; Tomiyama & Yoshikawa, 1987). ACRREx is a new method that shows designers where to look for innovative designs. First of all, we consider that creative or innovative design solutions are by definition solutions that never existed in the past. Such a solution corresponds to a “void” in our design object database. The ACRREx method first tries to categorize our design object database using categorizations that can be easily manipulated. Then, using these categorizations, it aims to look for “voids” where innovative design solutions can be found. ACRREx is an indirect method in that it does not generate new ideas but tells where new ideas can be found. However, it is a systematic procedural method that can be combined with other intuitive methods including bio-inspired design.

THE “ACRREX” CREATIVE DESIGN METHOD

LIMITS OF BRAINSTORMING

One of the most widely used methods to obtain initial design solutions is brainstorming (originally proposed by Osborn (1953)) in which designers spontaneously come up with possible solutions taken from their internal database of past experiences. To enhance this database we encourage students to

Figure 2. The ACRREx creative design method applied in wheeled vehicle design: abstracting & categorizing initial brainstorm solutions leads to triggering inputs for new brainstorm sessions.

search in various information sources for bio-inspiration. From brainstorming alone, however, students normally come up with a number of overall solutions that differ in many aspects from each other. Students tend not to look *into* these solutions and compare their fundamental differences with each other on a component level. Instead, they stay with the overall solutions and select from them the “best” one, which results in a sub-optimal design.

For example, suppose students have to design a wheeled vehicle that is fast, stable and simple of construction. During a brainstorm session, one student would come up with a bike, and another student with a car. Instead of looking at the fundamental differences between bike and car, students tend to make an overall comparison and to allocate scores to the design criteria to indicate to what extent these criteria are fulfilled. Instead of allocating scores, we teach students to dig deeper and to use the outcomes of a brainstorm session as a start to discover the entire solution space.

ABSTRACTING, CATEGORIZING AND FINDING “VOIDS”

The ACRREx method starts with a logical abstracting process to find the fundamental differences between the initial brainstorm solutions. What are the fundamental differences between a bike and a car seen from the perspective of propulsion? A bike has two wheels, a car four wheels, a bike is human-powered, a car motor-powered. Categorizing these differences in a table (Figure 2) results in two triggering questions: could there be a motor-powered device with two wheels, or a human-

Figure 3. The ACRREx creative design method applied in wheeled vehicle design: reflecting & extending leads to a series of new solutions that did not sprout up during the first brainstorm session.

powered device with four wheels? These questions form input for a new brainstorm session from which two new ideas (a kart and a motorbike) sprout up (left part of Figure 3). Alternating intuitive brainstorming with logic abstracting and categorizing results in new creative solutions that would not have been found by brainstorming alone.

REFLECTING, REFORMULATING AND EXTENDING

To get a better (preferably complete) overview of the solution space, we teach our students to try to make the categorization complete by reflecting, reformulating and extending. If devices with two and four wheels exist, why then not devices with one wheel or three wheels (right part of Figure 3) or maybe even zero wheels or an infinite amount of wheels? This gives input for a large set of new solutions, among which even caterpillar devices with fundamentally new working principles (with an “infinite” amount of wheels, ground contact not along 1-dimensional lines but along 2-dimensional surfaces). Finding new working principles could even lead to reformulating the original “wheeled vehicle” problem into the new challenge of optimizing the contact situation with the road, bringing the original design problem to a higher level.

FINDING FUNDAMENTAL DIFFERENCES

An important ingredient of the ACRREx method is the ability to find fundamental differences between a number of concept solutions. As some people are better in abstracting than others, we provide students with standard categorization criteria that can be used as tools to initiate out-of-box thinking to

reach a higher abstraction level. Below, three standard categorization criteria suitable for the field of mechanical engineering are listed. They may be less appropriate for other technical fields such as electrical or chemical engineering, which require their own specific categorization criteria.

Thinking in dimensions (0-3)

A way to initiate out-of-box thinking is to compare solutions from a dimensional perspective. A wheel has 1-dimensional contact with the world (line). What alternative for a wheel would have 0, 2 or 3-dimensional contact with the world? 0-Dimensional contact (point) can be generated with a foot. This solution points towards a walking robot as an alternative for a wheeled vehicle. 2-Dimensional contact (surface) is generated with a caterpillar, but also with a boat or plane (outer surface in contact with water or air). Could there be a device with 3-dimensional contact with the world?

Thinking in Degrees Of Freedom (0-6)

Matching dimensions with Degrees Of Freedom (DOF) initiates out-of-box thinking in the field of moving objects. A horizontal surface is 2-dimensional and defines 3 DOF: translating forward/backward, left/right and rotating horizontally. A car, however, has only 2 DOF (moving forward/backward and steering). As a result of this restriction, putting the car in a precise position and orientation (for example during parking) requires complex maneuvering to use the available DOF for indirect control of the missing DOF. Would it be possible to add a 3rd DOF to the car to compensate for this restriction? Space is 3-dimensional and defines 6 DOF (3 translations and 3

Figure 4. Example of a categorization from an MSc graduation student who used the ACRREx method in a state-of-the art review of microgripping methods “without intermediate layer” (e.g. without adhesives) within the applications biology, industry and medicine. Question marks indicate “voids” that have not yet been found or explored, creating openings for new R&D projects (Trommelen, et al., 2010).

rotations). As a plane has only 3½ DOF (moving forward (not backward), yaw, pitch and roll), complex maneuvering is required to reach a runway from the correct angle. Is there a plane that can also translate backward, up/down and left/right (the missing 2½ DOF)? The answer is a helicopter.

Thinking in forces instead of motions

People have a tendency to think in terms of motion: braking a car requires the wheels to be stopped. Out-of-box thinking is often stimulated by looking at a design from a force perspective (Herder, 1998; De Visser & Herder, 2000): braking a car requires a force opposite to the driving direction. Such a force can be generated by friction (brakes), but also by a parachute, a fan, a magnet, and so forth. A suitable alternative among these solutions could lead to an entirely new car design. Another example of thinking in motion is steering a boat by rotating the rudder.

Looking at this example from a force perspective results in steering the boat by applying a vertical torque. This torque can be generated by redirecting the water or the air (rudders in different variants, spritsails in sail ships, turbosails), but also by adding sideways propulsion devices to the ship (bow thrusters, fans on the deck), using gyroscopes, horizontal flywheels, magnets, etc.

EXAMPLES OF THE ACRREx METHOD

ABSTRACTING, CATEGORIZING AND FINDING “VOIDS”

We teach students to abstract and categorize their design concepts using short, precise expressions and simple, clear drawings to stress differences and similarities. This stimulates students to look through specific design details and to find fundamental working principles and differences, making it easier to complete a categorization and to find openings for

Figure 5. Example of a categorization from an MSc graduation student who used the ACRREx method in an elaborate patent search on mechanical joint types for steerable medical devices. By abstracting and categorizing, the student first created an overview of existing 2-dimensional joints (schematic drawings in top row) and then logically extended these joints to 3-dimensions (schematic drawings in bottom row). The patent search on these newly created joints revealed a large number of patents with a “void” at the third joint for which no patent yet exists (Pessers, 2011).

extension. Figure 4 shows an example in which one of our MSc graduation students categorized existing microgripping methods in nature, industry and medicine to find “voids” for new, yet unexplored alternatives (indicated with a question mark). Figure 5 shows another example in which an MSc graduation student categorized the existing patents on

mechanical joint types in order to find “voids” for 3-dimensional joint mechanisms that do not yet exist (indicated with a question mark).

REFLECTING, REFORMULATING AND EXTENDING

In the recent lecture series of our Bio-Inspired Design course, some student teams found rather ingenious,

Figure 6. Sketch of an interesting solution for the “non-slipping shoe” assignment for safe walking/running on icy surfaces, in which the student team stepped away from the original idea of reducing slip between sole and ice, and reformulated the assignment into a stability problem. This resulted in a tripod-like device positioned around the human body and ensuring under all circumstances that the person cannot fall.

unexpected solutions for their assignment by reflecting and reformulating the problem and stepping away from common solutions.

One student team worked on the design of a “non-slipping shoe” by which a person can walk and even run on icy surfaces without any risk of falling. Initially the students searched in the direction of a dedicated bio-inspired sole that generates grip with ice, but by reflecting and thinking on a more fundamental level they realized that avoiding falling is actually a stability problem. In the end they reformulated their original assignment and designed a tripod-like device positioned around the human body and ensuring that under all circumstances the person cannot fall (Figure 6).

Another student team worked on the design of a “single piece desk lamp”. Off-the-shelf desk lamps contain a foot, a movable arm and a lamp. The arm is used to put the lamp in a required position and orientation. Initially the students searched for alternative movable arm constructions, resulting in a number of interesting bio-inspired solutions but all having quite a lot of parts. By reflecting and thinking on a deeper level about what a desk lamp user actually wants, the students reformulated their assignment into “finding a way to position a light bulb in a room in any required position and

Figure 7. Demonstration model of an interesting solution for the “single piece desk lamp” assignment, in which the student team stepped away from the original idea of a lamp mounted to a movable arm and designed a lamp with an adhesive back that can be stuck to any surface in the room. In this simple model, Velcro was used to demonstrate the idea and the lamp was connected to an electric wire. In practice, it might be better to use a LED lamp with a rechargeable battery to generate more positioning freedom.

orientation with respect to a table”. By using this reformulated goal, the students were able to step away from the common idea of mounting a lamp on a movable arm, and they invented a lamp with an adhesive back that can be stuck to any surface (e.g. wall or ceiling) in a desired orientation (Figure 7).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the ACRREx method for creative design. It is a systematic method in that it dictates how to proceed, while it is an indirect method in that it does not directly tell how ideas can be generated. It tries to designate areas where creative design solutions could be found using categorizations that are obtained logically. Since creative design solutions are usually solutions that never existed in the past, those areas are obtained as “voids” in our design object database. The method can be used in combination with other systematic design methods such as the Pahl & Beitz method as well as with intuitive design methods such as brainstorming and bio-inspired design.

The ACRREx method was used in a classroom in which students worked on our Bio-Inspired Design course, as well as in MSc graduation research work in which students worked on design assignments. In both cases, those students who could apply the method appropriately could arrive at creative design solutions. The ACRREx method rejects intuition-only

designs. Although we believe that intuition can help creative design, there is no rationality and guarantee for exhaustiveness which are an essence of good engineering design. ACRREx helps designers to rationally and logically search for new classes of design solutions or entirely new solution fields. This fits better for engineering design education in which rationality and logic play more important roles than intuitions.

While the course Bio-Inspired Design is generally a success both in terms of feedbacks and the number of students, it still needs to be improved. One improvement is the course format, so that students have ample time to follow the ACRREx method. At this moment, students tend to be satisfied with their initial intuitive solutions due to time pressure.

Future work includes validations of the categorization method which is a crucial element of ACRREx. For this, we need to conduct a comparative study of the method with other methods such as TRIZ. In addition, we need to conduct more comprehensive studies to determine the effectiveness of ACRREx when used in the classroom: does ACRREx really help students to become more creative? Did ACRREx perform better in comparison with other methods? These are pedagogically interesting questions for future research.

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